

GENDER DISCRIMINATION IN RURAL NON-FARM EMPLOYMENT IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The position of women in the society is an index of its civilization. Women as human resource in India constitute about 50 per cent of the total population and about 77 per cent of them live in rural areas. The contribution of female labour force participation will reduce rural poverty. In fact the rural poor have no choice except to raise their work participation either through the use of child labour or the employment of female for earning additional income to meet the household requirements.

The percentage of female workforce in agriculture is declining. While that of manufacturing and services sectors is increasing. The share of non-farm female workers was 13.05 per cent in 1961 and it has declined to 10.88 per cent in 1991 then it increased and stood at 25.25 per cent in 2011. Between 1991 and 2011, the increase in share of females has been 9.3 percentage points.

The work participation rate is higher in rural areas than in urban areas. The work participation rate for rural females was only 30.98 per cent against 52.36 per cent of rural male work participation in 2011. A considerable variation has been found across the states and activities. A large number of female workers seem to take up jobs in rural non-farm sector in the occupational diversification process. The employment opportunities of females are growing in manufacturing, followed by services and construction, where as they are declining in trade in recent years. In terms of Clark-Kuznets thesis that India is on the path of economic development because the increase in the proportion of occupational structure of workforce from the primary sector to secondary and tertiary sectors had started moving steadily since the 1990s.

1. Introduction

One of the essential features of the structural changes observed in the process of economic development of the developed economies has been the decline in the proportion of workforce engaged in agriculture. Development economists have shown an abiding interest in the structural changes in the composition of income and employment. The premier objective of the development planning has been the diversification of rural economy away from agriculture to rural non-agriculture, leading to reduce the population pressure on agriculture. In the process of such development paradigm, the rural employment structure, as an outcome of economic growth as well as the government policies has begun to show its different dimensions in the following ways; declining workforce participation rates (WPRs); increasing diversification of rural workforce from agriculture to rural non-agriculture; and growing informality, casualisation and feminisation of rural employment. This shows that the growth of rural employment is not only declining but also the quality of rural employment is deteriorating over a period of time, and a good deal of employment opportunities are being generated in the rural non-farm sector. The contribution of female labour force participation will reduce rural poverty. In fact the rural poor have no choice except to raise their work participation either through the use of child labour or the employment of female for earning additional income to meet the household requirements. The impact of female labour force participation on non-farm employment is equally important, because it is now being considered as a strategy to solve the problems of unemployment and rural poverty.

2. Classification Of Work Force In India

The Census has divided the workers into ten major categories (since 1971). By clubbing together of 1 and 2, we get agricultural workers (farm workers) and by adding up all other categories, we get non-agricultural workforce (non-farm workers), from the classification of the workforce as follows:

1. Cultivators
2. Agricultural Labourers
3. Animal Husbandry, Plantation, fishing, forestry, etc.
4. Mining and Quarrying
5. (a) Household Industries (HHI)
(b) Non-household industries
6. Construction
7. Trade and Commerce
8. Transport, Storage and communication, and
9. Other services.

3. Activity Wise Distribution Of Female Workers In India

Agriculture is the most important activity of the female workforce (84%) in the rural areas, with the highest number of women workers engaged as agricultural labourers (Table-1).

However, the percentage of female workforce in agriculture is declining. Manufacturing and services are the other two sectors where women are employed in large numbers. The top ten manufacturing industries that employ women in large numbers are (a) Tobacco, (b) Cotton textiles, (c) Cashew nut processing, (d) Machine tools and parts, (e) Matches, explosives and fireworks, (f) Clay, glass, cement, iron and steel, (g) Drugs and medicines, (h) Grain mill and bakery, (i) Garments.

Table-1: Percentage Of Workers In Various Industrial Categories (2011)

Activity	% of Female Workers	
	Rural	Urban
Agriculture	84.0	14.5
Mining and Quarrying	0.4	0.4
Manufacturing	7.7	23.2
Electricity, Water et.	-	0.2
Construction	1.2	5.5
Trade, Hotels and Restaurant	2.3	16.4
Transport, storage	0.1	2.0
Services	4.3	37.8
Total	100.0	100.0

Source: NSSO, 55th round, 2011, Report No.455.

4. Rural Non-Farm Workers By Sex In India: Some Aspects

We observe the shares of non-farm (non-crop production) workers in the total rural workers and total workers (rural + urban) to capture changes in the occupational structure in India and deal with worker population ratios (WPRs) of non-agricultural workers both at rural and overall levels.

a. Share of Rural Non-Farm Workers In Overall Workers (Rural + Urban)

The rise in the share of non-farm employment is very crucial, for the structural change in the economy. Table-2 shows the shares of non-farm workers at the overall and rural economies in India. In 1961, the share of non-agricultural workers in rural India in total rural workforce was 17.85 per cent and it decreased to 17.53 per cent in 1971 and gradually increased to 27.26 per cent by 2011. This share among rural male workforce assumes 20.34 per cent in 1961 and declined to 18.82 per cent by 1971 and then gradually increased and stood at 33.26 per cent by 2011. Similarly, the share among females occupied 13.05 per cent in 1961 and it has declined till 1991, assuming 10.88 per cent in 1991. Between 1991 and 2011, the increase in shares has been by 7.8, 9.3 and 7.9 percentage points among males, females and persons respectively.

Now, the shares of non-agricultural workers at the aggregate level in India, among persons, it assumes 27.64 per cent in 1961 and it has gradually increased and stood at 43.26 per cent by 2011. Among the males, the share first decreased from 32.85 per cent in 1961 to 32.51 per cent in 1971, and then started rising from 1981 onwards and it ultimately reached to 47.84 per cent. In the case of females, the share occupied 16.91 per cent in 1961 and it has increased to 19.18 per cent in 1971, than it has gradually decreased to 17.57 per cent by 1991. There has been an abrupt jump from 17.57 per cent in 1991 to 32.25 per cent in 2011.

Table -2: Shares Of Non-Agricultural Workers By Sex In India, Rural And Overall (Rural+Urban)

Year	Rural			Overall (Rural+Urban)		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1961	20.34	13.05	17.85	32.57	16.91	27.64
1971	18.82	12.84	17.53	32.51	19.18	29.88
1981	20.92	11.89	18.32	36.37	18.06	31.65
1991	22.49	10.88	18.74	39.15	17.57	32.99
2001	30.32	20.14	26.67	47.84	28.06	41.60
2011	33.26	25.25	27.26	49.35	32.25	43.26

Source: Registrar General of India.

b. Workers Population Ratios Of Rural, Urban And Total Workforce By Sex In India

The gender-wise rural, urban and total work participation rates in India during 1961-2011 are shown in Table-3. The work participation rate is higher in rural areas than in urban areas. This is true both in the case of males and females. In 2011, work participation rate for rural males was 53.64 per cent and that for rural females 38.25 per cent. On the other hand, it has 53.65 per cent for urban males and 12.25 per cent for urban females. Since 1971, the work participation rate for rural males has been on the decline. It declined from 53.62 per cent in 1971 to 52.36 per cent in 2001 and now in 2011 it is 53.64. But it increased for rural females from 15.51 per cent to 30.98 per cent over the period. So far as urban males are concerned, their work participation rate was almost stationary at 49 per cent. But for urban females, it increase from 7.11 per cent to 11.55 per cent over the period due to the spread of education. The reason for higher work participation rate of both males and females in rural areas than in urban areas are larger concentration of population in rural areas and diversification of agriculture related activities like horticulture, pisciculture, dairy and poultry farming, etc. Moreover, both

men and women are engaged in productive activities in rural areas. Where as only men work and the majority of women remain at home in urban areas.

Table -3: Gender-Wise Rural And Urban Worker Population Rates In India

Year	Rural Workforce			Urban Workforce			Total Workforce		
	Male	Female	Persons	Male	Female	Persons	Male	Female	Persons
1961	58.22	31.42	45.07	52.40	11.09	33.48	57.12	27.96	42.98
1971	53.62	15.51	35.07	48.88	7.11	29.59	52.64	13.91	33.98
1981	53.65	22.77	38.59	48.88	8.28	29.89	52.50	19.49	36.56
1991	52.47	26.69	39.99	48.96	9.17	30.18	51.55	22.27	37.47
2001	52.36	30.94	41.97	50.85	11.55	32.23	51.93	25.68	39.26
2011	53.64	38.25	43.25	53.65	12.25	35.63	51.77	25.6	39.1

Source: Census Reports for various years.

c. Activity-Wise Distribution Of Rural Female Workers In Major States In India

In the case of female workers, the data provided in Table-4 show that while a rapid increase in manufacturing activities took place in West Bengal, Orissa and Bihar, and moderate increase in Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Punjab, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Haryana and Kerala during 2010-11 over 1993-94. On the other hand, Karnataka, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh and Assam experienced a sharp decline during the same period. In fact, a greater setback in the expansion of manufacturing activities for females took place only in Karnataka, Gujarat and Maharashtra.

In the case of construction, employment opportunities for female workers are not growing adequately. The share of female workers in construction showed a marginal increase in most of the states, where as a rapid decline took place in a few states namely West Bengal, Maharashtra, Karnataka and Rajasthan. It can also be noted that in a

drought year of 1987-88, their participation in construction, as compared to other activities, is found to be quite high. In the period of distress situation in agriculture reflected in low food grains production or under employment due to drought or any other, the first person who would shift to rural non-farm activities, particularly to construction are the female workers.

In the case of trading activities, eight states, viz., Haryana, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, West Bengal, Punjab and Kerala witnessed a marginal rise during 1993-94 to 2010-11. The remaining states, particularly Orissa, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra and Assam showed a steep decline during the same period.

In the situation of employment in services sector, the share of female workers increased rapidly in Assam, Kerala, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal. A sharp decline took place in Maharashtra, Haryana, Gujarat, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Rajasthan during 1993-94 to 2010-11. Thus, the data show that employment opportunities for female workers are growing in manufacturing, followed by services and construction, whereas they are declining in trade in recent years.

Table-4: Activity-Wise Distribution Of Female Workers In Major States In India During 1987-88 To 2010-2011

State	Manufacturing			Construction			Trade			Services		
	1987-88	1993-94	1999-2000	1987-88	1993-94	2010-11	1987-88	1993-94	2010-11	1987-88	1993-94	2010-2011
Andhra Pradesh	7.7	7.4	6.0	1.2	0.6	0.8	3.9	3.4	3.0	4.5	4.3	5.1
Assam	9.8	8.7	8.3	0.3	0.1	0.2	1.7	1.9	1.5	5.6	5.9	10.4
Bihar	4.1	3.9	8.5	0.8	0.2	0.5	1.8	1.9	1.8	2.1	1.6	3.3
Gujarat	3.6	4.1	2.2	16.9	1.4	1.8	0.8	1.0	1.6	2.6	2.6	1.8
Haryana	2.8	1.4	2.0	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.4	1.3	2.6	3.6	3.4	2.5
Himachal Pradesh	1.8	1.6	1.1	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.6	1.1	1.5	2.6
Karnataka	8.8	8.4	5.7	1.0	0.7	0.5	2.8	2.2	2.5	1.3	3.6	2.9
Kerala	19.0	19.2	19.3	0.8	2.1	2.7	3.7	3.6	3.7	9.4	11.1	13.6
Madhya Pradesh	5.0	3.2	4.2	1.7	0.4	1.2	1.0	0.7	1.0	0.9	0.9	1.9
Maharashtra	2.7	3.0	2.2	2.9	1.2	0.9	1.2	1.8	1.3	1.6	3.4	1.6
Orissa	11.4	7.5	12.9	2.5	1.1	1.8	3.4	2.9	1.9	3.5	2.6	2.8
Punjab	2.8	1.3	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.1	1.0	1.1	4.2	4.7	5.7
Rajasthan	4.1	1.4	2.8	10.2	2.5	2.4	0.6	0.7	0.6	1.3	1.5	1.4
Tamil Nadu	12.9	12.9	14.2	1.2	0.7	1.6	4.1	2.8	3.4	4.2	4.7	4.4

Uttar Pradesh	3.8	4.7	6.4	0.4	0.2	0.5	1.5	2.1	1.9	2.8	2.8	3.6
West Bengal	19.6	30.0	36.1	0.6	1.6	0.4	2.6	2.7	2.8	6.1	6.4	6.7
All India	6.9	7.0	7.7	2.7	0.9	1.2	2.1	2.1	2.0	3.0	3.4	4.3

5. Conclusions

The position of women in the society is an index of its civilization. Women as human resource in India constitute about 50 per cent of the total population and about 77 per cent of them live in rural areas. The contribution of female labour force participation will reduce rural poverty. In fact the rural poor have no choice except to raise their work participation either through the use of child labour or the employment of female for earning additional income to meet the household requirements.

The percentage of female workforce in agriculture is declining. While that of manufacturing and services sectors is increasing. The share of non-farm female workers was 13.05 per cent in 1961 and it has declined to 10.88 per cent in 1991 then it increased and stood at 20.14 per cent in 2011. Between 1991 and 2011, the increase in share of females has been 9.3 percentage points.

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- The occupational structure of rural population should be oriented towards secondary and tertiary sectors. For this, there is a need to spread educational, health and infrastructure facilities in rural areas suited to female employment.
- To reduce the pressure of population on land, village and small scale industries should be developed on a large scale in the rural areas so that the surplus labour force particularly female is absorbed in the secondary sector. This will also lead to change in the occupational structure of the labour force in favour of women. Besides, it will enable us to arrest rural-urban labour migration.

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